
TEACHING PRONUNCIATION TO THE YOUNG LEARNERS

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Annotation.

Current work deals with some issues of teaching pronunciation. What kind of skills can be included to language skills, how to define and prevent some problems of pronunciation errors. Steps to make language classroom more effective for communication skills.

Аннотация.

В данной работе рассматриваются некоторые вопросы обучения произношению. Какие навыки можно отнести к языковым навыкам, как определить и предотвратить некоторые проблемы ошибок произношения. Шаги, чтобы сделать языковой класс более эффективным для развития коммуникативных навыков.

Key words.

Language skills, pronunciation, intonation, communication, drilling, chaining, taping students' English.

Thinking more about students' pronunciation errors which barriers for successful communication can be an example why should we emphasize on teaching pronunciation. As Gerald Kelly notes that majority of teachers only pay attention to teaching grammar and vocabulary, and teaching pronunciation is rarely taken into consideration.²⁴¹ For example, if the learner says "grate" instead of "great", the listener will be confused. A learner, who makes always errors on producing the number of phonemes, a big problem may occur on speaking to and understanding the native speaker's speech. In spite of the fact that he has a huge knowledge of grammar and a large vocabulary, he may not be able to communicate. Gerald Kelly in his book also mentioned about the stress and its urgency in language learning. Giving some situations from Turkish learner classroom:

²⁴¹ Gerald Kelly How to teach pronunciation Pearson Education Limited 2000

Do you mind if I Open the window?

Here the stress is on the word /open/, where one could expect the stress on the first syllable of the word “window”. If the teacher wouldn’t have been aware of the situation and context, it could be seemed very rude.

Talking about intonation he gives the example of falling down intonation in the following sentence:

How long have you been in London?

In this example the listener couldn’t understand the question, where the intonation fell down on the word “been”. And as a result the person who was asking questions had to repeat it until the listener understood her.

Teaching pronunciation is important not only for making clearer speech, but also to improve students’ listening skills. When students know the correct pronunciation of the word, it will be easier to speak and understand the native speaker. As a teacher, we have to teach pronunciation, as the words may mean differently depending how we pronounce them. Language teachers’ first and major aim is to teach her students to communicate on that language. Our mission will fail if the learners’ accent is so bad that no one can understand them. In addition, teaching pronunciation is necessary since it’s embarrassing to ask someone to repeat themselves three times and still not understand them.²⁴²

Gerald Kelly mentioned two problems of teaching pronunciation. First is being neglected, and the second is when not neglected, it is a response to a specific problem in the classroom, not a strategically planned one.

The fact that pronunciation tends to suffer from neglect may not be due to teachers' lack of interest in the subject, but rather to a sense of how to teach it. Teachers with more experience admit that they lack knowledge of the theory of pronunciation, and they may say that they feel the need to improve their practical skills in teaching pronunciation. While trainees and less experienced teachers may be very interested in pronunciation, those concerned with grammar and vocabulary tend to take precedence. Language learners, on the other hand, often show considerable enthusiasm for pronunciation, which they believe will help them communicate better, which, ironically, even though both teachers and students are passionate about the subject, is often neglected.

Teachers of pronunciation need:

- A good grounding in theoretical knowledge;

²⁴² <https://teachingenglishgames.com/the-hows-and-whys-of-teaching-pronunciation/>

- Practical classroom skills;
- Access to good ideas for classroom activities

After having decided to make pronunciation an integral part of their teaching and adopting a model policy on what methods and activities teachers can use. The range is varied, from narrowly focused techniques such as drilling to broader activities such as encouraging students to notice specific pronunciation features in listening texts. In addition, there are two key aspects of learning pronunciation, namely teaching productive skills on the one hand and learning receptive skills on the other.

Drilling. One of the main ways to practice pronunciation in class is to practice it in its most basic form. Drilling simply involves the teacher saying the structure word and having the class repeat it. The primary role of the teacher in practice is to provide students with a model verbal phrase or structure to copy. Teachers usually practice "choral", which means inviting the whole class to repeat the element in unison. The choral exercise can help build confidence and gives students the opportunity to practice pronouncing the element being repeated relatively without putting it in place. This is usually followed by an individual exercise where students are asked to repeat one by one, this gives the teacher a chance to find out how well people can pronounce the subject being studied. Teachers usually choose people more or less randomly.

Chaining can be used for sentences that are difficult for students to pronounce as Isaac because they are long or contain complex words and sounds. The following examples show how the teacher isolates certain parts of a sentence, modeling them separately for students to repeat and gradually building up the sentence until it is complete.

Back chain

The sentence is drilled and built up from the end, gradually adding to its length. Certain parts may be drilled separately, if they present problems. Each part of the sentence is modelled by the teacher, and the students repeat.

...told him.

...would've...

...would've told...

I would've told him.

If I'd seen him...

If I'd seen him, I would've told him.

Front chain

The sentence is drilled and built up from the start, gradually adding to its length. Certain parts may be drilled separately, if they present problems. Each part of the sentence is modelled by the teacher, and the students repeat.

If I'd seen him...

If I'd seen him, I would've...

I would've...

I would've told him.

If I'd seen him, I would've told him.

In his book Gerald Kelly gave some pronunciation activities, which can be very helpful in planning the lesson where teachers' can may make, some accent on spelling and pronouncing skills of their students.

Homographs and homophones can provide useful facilities for such work. Homographs are words with the same spelling but different pronunciations. (*Why don't you read this book?* and *I've already read it;* *wind* as in weather and *wind* as in what you do to a clock). Homophones are words with the same pronunciation but different spellings. (*write* and *right*, *there*, *their* and *they're*; *fair* and *fare*) In the case of homophones, students listen to a sentence and must choose in which form the printed list of words in front of them is the word which was heard in the sentences. Correct spelling of a certain word in a sentence can also be done with classwork that concentrates on the properties or effects of certain letters when they appear in words.

Taping students' speech who speak English occasionally can pay dividends. Recordings can be made when students are practicing language and used for all kinds of language difficulties, but especially those related to pronunciation, if the teacher is sufficiently prepared students of a higher level, solving an identical problem. Alternatively, students can do the same task twice recording the first attempt will serve as a basis for working on pronunciation, the subsequent task will hopefully be more successful, and then the two attempts can be compared. Individual students may also be taped, especially if they have lingering pronunciation difficulties that are difficult to get rid of sound stress, and intonation may contrast with that of a native speaker, other students, or another L1 speaker who does not have the same difficulty.

Listening activities. Listening Comprehension exercises in textbooks are often designed to sound as realistic as possible. Speakers speak at normal speed and use natural language. They can play a key role in helping students notice the presence of pronunciation differences. In order to complete a listening task, students can pay attention to the meaning and pronunciation of a particular aspect of the language and practice it in a very controlled way. higher level of the third conditional sentence. The listening exercise can then ask students to listen to this area of language and listen to how it is used and say it in the context of a narrative or speak in a conversation.

As has been demonstrated in this paper, we may come to conclusion that, teachers shouldn't neglect teaching pronunciation. There are various types of techniques and methods which can be effective in teaching or improving students' pronunciation. We talked about a number of that methods and techniques here such as drilling, chaining, homographs and homophones, taping students' speech and listening comprehension exercises.

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